

Rac-31

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-137-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1022
Vial:	2	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 137 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	11.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/22/2021 9:28:11 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/22/2021 10:02:41 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.671	3264357	50.37	266248
2	8.762	3216136	49.63	227150

Asy-31 (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-139-4-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	1022
Vial:	3	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 139 4
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	11.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/22/2021 9:46:03 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/22/2021 10:01:02 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.670	195286	4.23	15733
2	8.760	4417414	95.77	311844